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Circular Construction Cluster, Open Days, Interactive Brochure #2: The WASTEie Journey

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As we pass the halfway mark of 2025, we're excited to share the latest updates from the RECONMATIC project and our growing network of collaborators.

From national Open Days to the expansion of the Circular Construction Cluster, from digital innovation tools to impactful conference presentations - our efforts to accelerate circularity in construction are gaining momentum. Let's take a look at what we've been working on!

Circular Construction Cluster: Recent Highlights

As part of our ongoing efforts to drive systemic change in the construction sector, the **Circular Construction Cluster (CCC)** – initiated by the RECONMATIC project and coordinated by **Future Needs** – continues to grow and strengthen.

CCC Member Meeting: Building Synergies Across Europe and Beyond

In May, the CCC held its latest member meeting, bringing together a vibrant network of organisations and EU-funded projects. The meeting focused on:

- Exploring synergies between members
- Welcoming new organisations to the cluster
- Continuing the shared mission to advance circularity in construction

CCC Member Meeting in May 2025

The CCC now includes 9 active members, all committed to knowledge exchange and collaboration to maximise collective impact:

RECONMATIC, CircularB, REDOL EU Project, RecycleBIM Project, Camacol Antioquia, Western Balkans Circular Economy Hub, DeCO2 Horizon Europe Project, Institut Cirkulární Ekonomiky, z. ú., Alianza Latinoamericana Circular en el Sector de la Construcción

EU Green Week Partner Event: Spotlight on the Western Balkans

In June, CCC members RECONMATIC and the Western Balkans Circular Economy Hub co-organised an online session as part of the EU Green Week 2025. The session brought together experts, researchers, and policymakers to share tools, case studies, and strategies for enabling more circular practices in construction, with a particular focus on the Western Balkans.

Building Circular Futures in the Balkans: EU Green Week'25 Partner Event Recap + Recording

Building Circular Futures in the Balkans: EU Green Week'25 Partn...

On June 10th, 2025, the Building Circular Futures: Advancing Circular Economy in Construction in the Western Balkans partner event marked a...

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Welcoming INCIEN to the Cluster

In 2025, CCC welcomed a new member: INCIEN from the Czech Republic, further strengthening the Cluster's reach and knowledge exchange across Europe.

"INCIEN plays a key role in translating European-level ambitions into practical and scalable solutions at the local level. By participating in the CCcluster, we hope to deepen our engagement with European peers, share policy insights, and co-develop systemic solutions for the built environment." - **Ben Hague**, Head of the Research Team at INCIEN

RECONMATIC Open Days

This spring, RECONMATIC hosted two successful Open Day events in Greece and Spain, bringing together professionals, policymakers, and academics to discuss the future of circular construction. These national-level events showcased innovative approaches to construction and demolition waste (CDW) management, digitalisation, and circular economy solutions.

Thessaloniki, Greece, March 6, 2025. The event was held in Greek and co-organised with the **TEE TKM** under the auspices of the Department of Civil Engineering at **Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)**.

Key highlights included:

- Welcoming remarks from political leaders, local authorities, and academic representatives
- Discussions on the role of digital tools and AI in CDW tracking and reuse
- Case studies and emerging solutions from RECONMATIC and national initiatives

Moments from the RECONMATIC Open Day in Thessaloniki, Greece.

Madrid, Spain March 13, 2025. The 6th RECONMATIC Open Day was organised by project partners **ICATALIST S.L**, **AEICE Clúster de Hábitat Eficiente**, **ITC - Instituto de Tecnología Cerámica**, **RECSO reciclados sostenibles** and **TECNALIA Research & Innovation**.

Participants explored:

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- Practical tools and digital platforms developed within the RECONMATIC project
- National and EU-level strategies to support circularity in construction
- Opportunities for collaboration among industry, research, and public sector actors

Moments from the RECONMATIC Open Day in Madrid, Spain

Progress on the Training Material

The RECONMATIC project team is currently developing online educational materials to share our knowledge and findings with a wider audience. Led by our partner **South Bohemian Agency for Support to Innovation (JAIP)**, this initiative will make the latest insights and results from our work easily accessible to professionals and anyone interested in circular construction and demolition practices.

These resources will include:

- Online modules based on real-world case studies
- Practical training on circular CDW management
- Partner-country training events aimed at professionals across sectors (e.g. architects, construction companies, waste managers)

Be the first to access our free training modules and get exclusive updates on local training events. 🗓️ [Register your interest here.](#)

RECONMATIC on the International Stage

RECONMATIC was presented at Digital Construction Week in...

RECONMATIC was presented at Digital Construction Week in London earlier this month. 🗓️ 🗣️ Our project partners, Ali Nader Saad and D...
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Feeling grateful and excited to be presenting my research and...

Feeling grateful and excited to be presenting my research and RECONMATIC at the Sustainable Built Environment Conference Zürich (SBE25) in the...

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RECONMATIC at RECYCLING 2025

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RECONMATIC once again participated in the traditional national conference Recycling 2025: Circular Economy in Civil Engineering, Recycling,...

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Throwback to last month, when our partners represented RECONMAT...

Throwback to last month, when our partners represented RECONMATIC at Futurebuild 2025 in London — an event that brought together...

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Latest on Our Blog

💡 **Demo #2: Advancing Circularity in Railway Construction.**

RECONMATIC Demonstrator #2, led by **Italferr S.p.A.** is piloting circular tools in a real-world railway construction context. With waste from rail infrastructure projects, including steel, ballast, concrete, and contaminated soils, this pilot explores:

- Material mapping and reuse
- Waste prediction
- BIM-based digital integration

💡 **Bridging the Digital Gap in CDW: Introducing DIMS.**

In a sector that produces millions of tonnes of waste annually, RECONMATIC introduces **DIMS (Digital Information Management System)** to close the digitalisation gap. Authored by **Ali Nader Saad, (The University of Salford)** the article dives into how BIM, IoT, AI, DPPs, and UIDs power DIMS to support:

- Real-time material tracking
- Lifecycle transparency
- Circular decision-making in construction

RECONMATIC Interactive Brochure #2: The WASTEie Journey

This issue takes a deep dive into the work of **BIMBox** one of the RECONMATIC partners, who have been collaborating closely with **Morgan Sindall Construction** and the **The University of Salford** on four key areas of the project. In this **interactive brochure**, you'll explore their journey across the following topics:

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- **Navigating the WASTEie Journey** – Discover the process map that tracks how and when construction and demolition waste is generated throughout a building's lifecycle.
- **Implementing Information Management** – Learn how the team is integrating waste data into everyday workflows to make waste tracking more efficient and useful.
- **Using a Data Dictionary to Enrich the IFC Schema** – Dive into how standardised data tools like the buildingSMART Data Dictionary are being used to make waste information clearer and easier to share.
- **The Future of Construction Waste Management** – Take a look ahead at how digital tools, openBIM standards, and case studies are helping to move the industry toward zero waste.

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Meet Us at the Upcoming Event

📍 **ERSCP 2025** | *September 18–22* Join us at the 22nd European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production #ERSCP2025, where RECONMATIC Project Coordinator **Jan Valentin** plays an active role in the Steering Committee.

🤝 **Want to collaborate with RECONMATIC?** Get in touch with our dissemination leader, **Egle Joneliunaite** from **Future Needs**, to explore potential synergies and join us in shaping the future of circular construction!

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